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Research Article

ROLE OF CT UROGRAPHY IN CASE OF HAEMATURIADr Mehreen Nawab¹, Dr Ayesha Ihsan², Dr Ayesha Usman³¹Rawalpindi Medical University²Lahore Medical and Dental College³Shalamar Medical and Dental College**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Hematuria can signify serious disease such as bladder cancer, upper urinary tract urothelial cell carcinoma (UUT-UCC), renal cell cancer or urinary tract stones. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the role of CT urography in case of haematuria. This descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University during August 2019 to March 2020. Fifty patients with complaint of haematuria referred from various wards and outpatient departments of this institution were included in our study. A complete patient history regarding the chief complaints was taken and a thorough clinical examination was carried out after taking a written informed consent. Hematuria has a wide range of causes including urinary tract infections, calculi, trauma, renal parenchymal disease, metastatic disease, and urothelial and renal neoplasia. The most common primary malignancies associated with hematuria are renal cell carcinoma (RCC); transitional cell carcinoma (TCC); prostate cancer; and, less commonly, squamous cell carcinoma. RCC is the most common malignant neoplasm of the kidney, representing up to 90% of renal neoplasms and up to 3% of all neoplasms. It is concluded that in imaging patients with hematuria, radiography has no role in the detection of renal or ureteric neoplasms and its choice for the detection of urinary calculi is now questionable with the advent of low-dose MDCT.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hematuria can signify serious disease such as bladder cancer, upper urinary tract urothelial cell carcinoma (UUT-UCC), renal cell cancer or urinary tract stones. CT urography is a rapidly evolving technique made possible by recent advances in CT technology. CT urography is defined as CT examination of the kidneys, ureters and bladder with at least one series of images acquired during the excretory phase after intravenous contrast administration [1]. The reasoning for using CT urography to investigate hematuria is based on its high diagnostic accuracy for urothelial cell carcinoma (UCC) and favorable comparison with other imaging techniques [2].

The optimum diagnostic imaging strategy for patients with hematuria at high-risk for UCC involves the use of CT urography as a replacement for other imaging tests (ultrasonography, intravenous urography, or retrograde ureteropyelography) and as a triage test for cystoscopy, resulting in earlier diagnosis and improved prognosis of bladder cancer, UUT-UCC, renal cell cancer and stones [3].

Hematuria is one of the most common presentations of patients with urinary tract diseases; therefore, it is a common reason for urinary tract imaging. The most appropriate imaging for adult patients presenting with hematuria as a symptom is reviewed in this article, based on the Appropriateness Criteria from the American College of Radiology [4]. The American Urologic Association (AUA) has previously published guidelines regarding the use of imaging in asymptomatic hematuria. The AUA guidelines recommended upper tract imaging for low- and high-risk patients with microscopic hematuria, defined as three or more red blood cells per high-power field from two of three properly collected urinalysis specimens. Patients whose urinary tracts have no detectable pathology normally release small amounts of blood into urine, so that one or two red cells per high-power field may normally be visible upon microscopic examination of the spun sediment. This fact, together with the low prevalence of clinically detectable disease in patients with asymptomatic microscopic hematuria, has led investigators to suggest that such minimal microhematuria in an asymptomatic young adult needs no evaluation [5].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the role of CT urography in case of haematuria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University during August 2019 to March 2020. Fifty patients with complaint of haematuria referred from various wards and outpatient departments of this institution were included in our study. A complete patient history regarding the chief complaints was taken and a thorough clinical examination was carried out after taking a written informed consent. Relevant laboratory investigations were done. Patients with haematuria were evaluated by ultrasonography (US). Plain x-ray KUB was performed in 20 patients. Multidetector computed tomography was performed in US positive cases, in symptomatic patients with negative US scans and in those with suboptimal US scans.

RESULTS:

Hematuria has a wide range of causes including urinary tract infections, calculi, trauma, renal parenchymal disease, metastatic disease, and urothelial and renal neoplasia. The most common primary malignancies associated with hematuria are renal cell carcinoma (RCC); transitional cell carcinoma (TCC); prostate cancer; and, less commonly, squamous cell carcinoma. RCC is the most common malignant neoplasm of the kidney, representing up to 90% of renal neoplasms and up to 3% of all neoplasms. Urothelial tumors represent only 10% of upper urinary tract neoplasms; however, bladder cancer is the fourth most common cancer in the United States. Synchronous tumors occur in 2% of renal TCC lesions and 9% of ureteric TCC lesions. The multifocal and bilateral nature of TCC mandates a thorough evaluation of the urothelium and makes urothelial imaging challenging for the radiologist.

Maximum cases were seen in 51-60 years age group – 15 cases (30%) followed by 10 cases (20%) in the age group of 61-70 years. Seven cases (14%) were seen in the age group of 31-40 years and six cases (12%) in the age group of 41-50 years. The youngest patient was 19 years old and the eldest 74 years old. More than one of the associated symptoms was present in many patients with haematuria. The most frequently encountered symptom was abdominal pain in 24 patients (48%). Anaemia was present in 30 patients (60%). Fever was also observed in 10 patients (20%). History of diabetes was present in five cases. Out of these five cases, two belonged to the inflammatory group. Loss of appetite was another important clinical feature in malignant cases (30%). One patient presented with history of road side accident with severe head and abdominal injuries (Figure 1). Out of the 30 patients in our study, 14 (28%) presented with

haematuria associated with pain and 36 (72%) with painless haematuria.

Table 01: Role of CT urography in case of haematuria.

	No. of patients with ultrasound diagnosis	No. of patients with MDCT diagnosis
Bladder carcinoma	9	9
UTUC	-	2
RCC	3	3
Prostatic carcinoma	1	1
UUT-stones	8	8
Bladder stones	2	2
BPH	2	2
Cystitis	1	1
Renal injury	1	1
Urinary bladder diverticulum	1	1
Chronic pyelonephritis	1	1
Acute pyelonephritis	2	2
Normal	19	17

DISCUSSION:

Radiologic evaluation will almost always be accompanied by cystoscopy because many bleeding urinary tract lesions arise in the bladder and lower urinary tract, and no imaging technique is completely satisfactory for ruling out disease at these sites. A complete history, physical examination, urinalysis, and appropriate blood tests should precede or accompany the imaging examinations [6]. At the time of cystoscopy, bilateral retrograde pyelography (in which iodinated contrast is injected through catheters placed in the ureters during cystoscopy and plain radiographs are obtained) is often employed to evaluate the upper tracts for pathology.

There is no universal agreement about the optimal imaging work-up of hematuria. Traditionally, excretory urography (intravenous pyelogram) was the standard, but the establishment of this practice

preceded the development of high-quality ultrasonography, CT, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [7]. Recently, multidetector CT scans, in which each rotation of the radiography beam produces multiple sets of images instead of just one set, have become routine [8]. They provide cross-sectional images and can be reformatted to demonstrate the urinary tract in a manner similar to traditional intravenous pyelograms. Similarly, MRI can be used to detect urinary tract abnormalities, but has limited use because of its expense and the lack of data supporting its use [9].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that in imaging patients with hematuria, radiography has no role in the detection of renal or ureteric neoplasms and its choice for the detection of urinary calculi is now questionable with the advent of

low-dose MDCT. Ultrasound remains an important diagnostic tool for the evaluation of hematuria in children and in low-risk patients and for characterizing bladder abnormalities and cystic renal lesions.

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